

Studies in Carbohydrates. Part X. Hydrolysis Products of the Gum from Drum Stick Plant (*Moringa Pterygosperma*)

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From the hydrolysates of the gum from Drum Stick plant (*Moringa pterygosperma*), obtained under mild acidic conditions, an aldotriuronic acid and a partially hydrolysed gum, designated as "a degraded gum", have been isolated. The structural features of these products are discussed on the basis of their methylation studies.

As shown previously¹, the gum from Drum Stick plant was composed of L-arabinose, D-galactose, D-glucuronic acid, and a methylpentose (traces). A colouring matter was also reported¹. As the gum could not be purified by usual methods, purification of the crude gum was carried out by treating it with alkali at 90° for a couple of hours and isolating the gum after acidification of the thick cold alkaline extract by addition of ethanol. Two to three similar treatments yielded the gum as a pale rosy powder (ca. equiv. 2250). It contained D-galactose, L-arabinose, and D-glucuronic acid in the molar proportion of 6:8:1 respectively. The chromatographic examination of the hydrolysate did not show presence of a methylpentose.

Hydrolysis of the gum by 3% (w/v) sulphuric acid gave an aldotriuronic acid {equiv. 520, uronic anhydride 33.9%, galactan 62.1%; $[\alpha]^{25}_D + 28^\circ$ ($c=2$ in water)} . On hydrolysis it yielded D-galactose and D-glucuronic acid only. The methyl ester of the fully methylated acid {OMe 50.2%; $[\alpha]^{25}_D - 29.75^\circ$ ($c=2$ in chloroform)} on hydrolysis yielded (i) 2, 3, 4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose (anilide m.p. and mixed m.p. 165°) and (ii) 2, 3, 4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucuronic acid (methyl ester of 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-saccharolactone, m.p. and mixed m.p. 107°). These results indicate that the uronic acid should possess 1→6β linkages and its structure should be *O*-β-D-glucopyranosyl-uronic acid-(1→6)-β-D-galactopyranosyl-(1→6)-D-galactose. This structure was also supported by its periodate oxidation.

Hydrolysis of the gum by very mild acid (0.02*N*-H₂SO₄) removed all the arabinose units and a stable degraded gum, free of arabinose, was obtained from the hydrolysate as a white powder {equiv. 1150; $[\alpha]^{25}_D + 27.5^\circ$ ($c=2$ in water); galactan 82.0%, uronic anhydride 15.3%; iodine number 4.2}. Hydrolysis of the degraded gum by 10% (w/v) H₂SO₄ gave D-galactose and the above described aldotriuronic acid. Periodate oxidation of the degraded gum by the procedure of Jones² liberated seven molecules of formic acid and consumed fourteen molecules of sodium metaperiodate per equivalent of the gum. The methyl ester of the fully methylated degraded gum {OMe 43.1%; $[\alpha]^{25}_D 0^\circ$ } on

1. Ingle and Bhide, this *Journal*, 1964, 31, 930.

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3393.

hydrolysis yielded 2, 3, 4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose (I) and 2, 3, 4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucuronic acid (II) (amide m. p. and mixed m. p. 185°).

The above results indicate that the degraded gum is composed of D-galactose and D-glucuronic acid in the molar proportion of 6:1. Removal of arabinose during mild hydrolysis suggests that arabinose units are presumably joined to the degraded gum in the furanose form (if they are the integral part of the gum). The isolation of an aldotriuronic acid from the total gum as well as the degraded gum indicates that the aldotriuronic acid is the most resistant part of the product. Methylation studies indicate that the degraded gum is composed of 1 → 6 linked D-galactose and D-glucuronic acid residues with the latter present as non-reducing end groups. The low optical rotations of the products as well as the methylated derivatives suggest β-linkages. Hence the probable structure of the degraded gum is D-Gp A 1-(6-β-D-Galp 1-)₅-6-D-Galp.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chromatographic separations of simple sugars were carried out by the descending method on Whatman No. 1 filter paper using authentic samples of sugars side by side. The solvent systems used for chromatography were butanol³: ethanol: water: ammonia (50 : 40 : 9 : 1) and ethyl acetate: acetic acid: water (9:2:2; v/v). The chromatograms were developed by Novellie's reagent³. Methylated sugars were separated by using butanol³: petroleum ether (100-120°) (3:7; v/v) and aniline hydrogen phthalate was used for detecting these sugars.

Purification of the Gum.—The gum, isolated as described previously¹, was found to contain a large amount of a colouring matter as well as a cellulosic material; hence it was designated as a crude gum and was further purified as described below. The crude gum (100 g.) was kept in contact with 1*N*-NaOH solution (2 litres) overnight at room temperature when it formed a thick jelly. It was heated on a water bath at 90° for 2 hrs. with occasional stirring. The jelly, thus obtained, was cooled to room temperature and squeezed through a piece of muslin. The filtrate was acidified to Congo red with HCl (dil. 1:1, v/v). Ethanol (≈ 4 litres) was added to it with stirring till the gum separated as a flocculent precipitate. The latter was separated from the ethanolic reddish filtrate and triturated with fresh ethanol when it was obtained as a reddish powder. After two or three similar treatments the gum was obtained as a pinkish white powder which on hydrolysis with 10% H₂SO₄ (w/v) showed presence of L-arabinose, D-galactose, and D-glucuronic acid. [Found (oven dry basis): ash, 0.2%; cellulose, 1.5%; pentosan, 49.1%; galactan, 38.5%; uronic anhydride, 8.04%; equiv., 2250 (ca.). A polysaccharide having units of D-galactose, L-arabinose, and D-glucuronic acid in the molar proportion 6:8:1 respectively requires pentosan, 47.2%; galactan, 42.8%; uronic anhydride, 7.9%; equiv., 2222].

Isolation of Aldotriuronic Acid.—A viscous solution of the gum (100 g.), obtained by keeping the gum in contact with water (1500 ml) overnight, was diluted to 2 litres by

3. *Nature*, 1950, 166, 745.

adding 2.5*N*-H₂SO₄ (500 ml), thereby making the solution 3% (w/v) w. r. t. sulphuric acid. The solution was heated on a water bath at 90° and the hydrolysis was followed iodometrically and polarometrically. Reducing power and rotation did not change appreciably after 24 hrs. A small amount of a flocculent precipitate was obtained which was removed by filtration and the slightly reddish filtrate was neutralised with barium carbonate. The filtrate and washings were concentrated to 250 ml and added to ethanol (1 litre) when the barium salt of uronic acid/s precipitated. The precipitate was washed with ethanol (80%, v/v) till it became free of reducing sugars. The barium salt was dissolved in water (200 ml), treated with charcoal, and filtered. The barium salt was precipitated by ethanol from the filtrate as a white powder which on hydrolysis with 10% H₂SO₄ furnished D-galactose and D-glucuronic acid only. (Found: Ba, 12.7%. A barium salt of aldatriuronic acid composed of two units of galactose and one unit of glucuronic acid requires Ba, 11.7%).

To the barium salt (5 g.), dissolved in water (25 ml), a requisite quantity of H₂SO₄ (dil.) was added to liberate the acid and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated at 40° under reduced pressure to 10 ml and absolute ethanol (100 ml) was added when the acid separated as a white powder, which on hydrolysis with 10% H₂SO₄ for 50 hrs. at 90° gave D-galactose and D-glucuronic acid. { Found: C, 41.5; H, 5.9; galactan, 62.1; uronic anhydride, 33.9%; equiv., 520; iodine No., 36.0; [α]_D²⁰+28° (c, 2 in water). An aldatriuronic acid containing two units of galactose and one unit of glucuronic acid requires C, 41.7; H, 5.8; galactan, 64.1; uronic anhydride, 33.84%; equiv., 518; iodine No., 36.6 }.

Methylation of Aldatriuronic Acid.—Barium salt of aldatriuronic acid (25 g.) was dissolved in water (200 ml) and 2*N*-H₂SO₄ (200 ml) was added to it at room temperature. The solution was filtered and the filtrate and washings were methylated by dimethyl sulphate (125 ml) and 30% NaOH solution (125 ml) with dropwise addition during 5 hrs. when the solution became non-reducing. It was acidified till faintly alkaline and concentrated to 200 ml on a water bath when a large quantity of sodium sulphate separated. It was filtered and the filtrate was remethylated as described above. After five similar treatments the solution was acidified to Congo red, extracted with chloroform, and the methylated acid was isolated by evaporation of the dried (Na₂SO₄) extract; yield 14 g. { Found: OMe, 37.22%; [α]_D²⁰-13.9° (c=2 in CHCl₃) }. The methylated acid was treated with methyl iodide (200 ml) and silver oxide (30 g.). Two similar treatments gave a product having OMe 50.2%; [α]_D²⁰-22.4° (c=2 in CHCl₃); yield 11.5 g. Any further treatment with methyl iodide and silver oxide did not change its OMe content. The product was distilled under reduced pressure when the major portion distilled between 190° and 210° at 0.5 mm; yield 6.2 g. { Found: C, 51.5; H, 7.9; OMe 50.2; equiv., 664; [α]_D²⁰ 29.7° (c=2 in CHCl₃). The methyl ester of fully methylated aldatriuronic acid containing two units of galactose and one unit of glucuronic acid requires C, 51.8; H, 7.73; OMe, 50.9%; equiv., 658 }.

Methanolysis of the Ester and Isolation of Different Sugars.—The ester (2.5 g.) was dissolved in methanolic HCl (7%, 100 ml) and refluxed for 70 hrs. when the optical rotation changed to +64.2° and remained constant. It was neutralised with silver carbonate and filtered. The filtrate was treated with hydrogen sulphide, filtered, and concentrated under reduced pressure to a syrup which was distilled. Fraction I: b. p. 120-30°/0.5 mm; Fraction II: b. p. 130-40°/0.2 mm. Both fractions were mixed and hydrolysed by 4% HCl (w/v) for 3 hrs. at 90°. The acid was neutralised with silver carbonate, the filtrate

treated with H_2S followed by barium carbonate, and then filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to dryness. The dry powder was extracted with ether (sodium dried) several times. The ether extract gave a syrup (A) containing non-acidic reducing sugars, whereas the residue (A) was the barium salt of methylated uronic acid.

Identification of Methylated Sugars

2,3,4-Tri-O-methyl-D-galactose.—The syrup (A) (1.0 g.) was found to contain OMe 41.5% and showed the presence of only one sugar. It was identified as 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-galactose by running the authentic sample side by side. It was characterised by preparing its anilide: m.p. and mixed m.p. 165°.

2,3,4-Tri-O-methyl-D-glucuronic Acid.—The barium salts (residue A, 0.5 g.) had OMe, 31.1%; Ba 22.1%; $[\alpha]_D^{20} +50.2'$, ($c=2$ in water). The acid was shown to be 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-glucuronic acid by oxidising it with bromine and converting it to 2,3,4-tri-O-methylsaccharolactone; m.p. and mixed m.p. 107°.

Periodate Oxidation of Aldotriouronic Acid.—The acid (0.2 g.) was placed in a stoppered bottle and dissolved in distilled water (50 ml). A solution of sodium metaperiodate (35 ml, 0.2M) was added to it. The total mixture was made to 100 ml and kept at 0° in the dark with occasional stirring. A definite quantity was drawn at intervals and the formic acid liberated was determined by titration after decomposing the excess of periodate by ethylene glycol. At the same time the consumption of sodium metaperiodate was also determined. It was found that the first stage of oxidation was complete during 16 hrs. and one equivalent of the acid liberated six molecules of formic acid and consumed eight molecules of sodium metaperiodate, which was in complete accord with the expectations based on the proposed structure.

Isolation of the Degraded Gum.—The purified gum (20 g.) was added to 0.02N- H_2SO_4 (400 ml) and kept overnight. The suspension was heated on a water bath at 90°. The hydrolysis was followed by Willstätter and Schudel's method⁴. $N/10-I_2$ required for 1g. of the gum at different hours: 20.1 ml (4 hrs.), 40.3 ml (8 hrs.), 55.0 ml (12 hrs.), 70.5 ml (16 hrs.), 72.6 ml (20 hrs.), 73.1 ml (24 hrs). The hydrolysate after 20 hrs. was filtered and added to ethanol (1.6 litres) when the degraded gum formed a flocculent precipitate (yield 8 g.). It was filtered and triturated with 90% ethanol (v/v) several times till it became free of reducing sugars. It is non-reducing and fairly soluble in water. On hydrolysis with 3% H_2SO_4 it gave the above described aldotriouronic acid {equiv. 522; $[\alpha]_D^{20} +27.5'$ ($c=2$ in water)}. (Found: galactan, 82.0%; uronic anhydride, 15.3%; equiv., 1150; iodine No., 4.2). The gum is composed of six molecules of galactose. One molecule of glucuronic acid per equivalent of the gum requires galactan 83.1%; uronic anhydride 15.1%; equiv. 1166; iodine No. 17.3. The periodate oxidation of the degraded gum by the method of Jones⁵ liberated seven molecules of formic acid and consumed fourteen molecules of sodium metaperiodate per equivalent of the degraded gum (*i.e.* 1150).

Preparation and Fractionation of the Methylated Degraded Gum.—The degraded gum (15 g.) was methylated 4 to 5 times with NaOH and dimethyl sulphate according to the procedure described under the methylation of aldotriouronic acid. The methylated

gum acid (OMe 35.5%, yield 10 g.) was further methylated using methyl iodide and silver oxide till the product had a constant methoxyl content (usually three times). { Found: OMe, 42.2%; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, 0°; yield 8.0 g. }. The product (7.5 g.) was separated in different fractions by dissolving the methylated gum in chloroform (20 ml) and adding petroleum ether (b.p. 100-20°, 50 ml) each time. Yields of OMe in fractions are: (I): 38.4%, 1.2 g. (II): 41.9%, 1.1 g. (III): 43.1%, 3.5 g. (IV): 43.0%, 1.5 g. All the above fractions on hydrolysis and chromatographic examination gave similar pattern of sugars; therefore fraction (III) was used for further work.

Hydrolysis of the Methylated Degraded Gum and Identification of Methylated Sugars.—Fraction (III) (3 g.) was dissolved in methanolic HCl (4%, 60 ml) and heated in a sealed tubes at 100° for 24 hrs. The contents of the tubes were transferred to a flask and aqueous 4% HCl (300 ml) was added to it. The mixture was hydrolysed and worked up as described under aldouronic acid. The non-acidic reducing sugars were obtained as a syrup (A) (24 g.) and the barium salt of the methylated uronic acid was obtained as a residue (A). The syrup (A) had OMe 41.3%; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 142^\circ \rightarrow +114^\circ$ ($c=1$ in water). The chromatographic examination indicated only one sugar which ran side by side with the authentic sample of 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose. It was characterised as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose by preparing its anilide (m. p. and mixed m. p. 185°). The residue (A) had OMe 31.0%; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 50.1^\circ$. The chromatographic examination indicated the presence of 2, 3, 4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucouronic acid. It was confirmed by preparing its amide through its ester (m. p. and mixed m. p. 185°).